

AIR TRANSPORT SERVICE IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM

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Abstract: *Transport is one of the most important components of the material base of the economy of any country. The main share in the total composition of transport services belongs to air transport. Most tourists, especially long-distance travelers, use aviation services.*

Key words: *Air transport, air containers, aviation, service share.*

Nowadays, transport is one of the most important components of the economy of a developing country with a highly developed economic and social base. Transport ensures the normal operation of the economy, increases the efficiency of social production, creates conditions for the rational distribution of production forces throughout the country, taking into account the most appropriate approximation of enterprises in various sectors of the economy to the sources of raw materials and raw materials. It allows the development of industries such as areas of product consumption, production specialization and cooperation, and trade. Transport is the leading factor of tourism development. Transport has a great role in solving social problems, ensuring business, cultural and tourist trips of the population, developing cultural exchange within the country and abroad.

Transport ensures the development of international transport. And economic relations facilitate mutually beneficial exchanges between different countries. Historically, the formation of transport systems of different countries is influenced by

their geographical location, natural potential, and often climate and landscape features. This led to the formation of transport and technical bases that are most rationally used in the conditions of a certain region and state.

With the development of tourism, transport routes are constantly expanding, because the increase in demand for travel has a positive effect on the development of transport infrastructure. Transport, in turn, allows to expand the geography of travel. There is a beneficial and beneficial cooperation between the two parties. Transport services are one of the main types of services in tourism. They occupy the main share in the price structure of the species. Depending on the duration and distance of the trip, this share (in most cases) is from 20 to 60%. The main share in the total composition of transport services belongs to air transport. Most tourists, especially long-distance travelers, use aviation services. At the same time, the plane can be called, in a figurative sense, the transport of individuals. The largest flow of tourists traveling for resort, business, entertainment and educational purposes are individual tourists. And they often use air transport.

According to statistics, the growth rate of popularity of air transport is higher than that of road transport, which is related to the expansion of the geography of travel and the existing stable trend to reduce travel time in favor of their frequency (growth). short-term long-term trips).

All this is the reason why the tourist business pays great attention to air transport. Airplanes are the most popular mode of transportation in the world. The same can be said about air travel in tourism, and there are several reasons for this:

- Aviation is the fastest and most convenient form of transport for long-distance travel;
- Service on flights has an attractive appearance for tourists;
- Airlines, directly and through international booking and booking networks, pay travel agencies a commission for each seat booked on the plane, which encourages them to choose air transport.

To start talking about the advantages and disadvantages of air travel advantages and disadvantages of air travel, we need to come to define air transport, passengers,

cargo, which is a service that helps us move from one place to another. Air transport is for commercial purposes, and originally this type of transport was only intended for the movement of people. As the design of both air containers and cargo-only aircraft has changed, the volume of cargo has increased significantly. In addition, advances in navigation as well as telecommunications have allowed this to develop tremendously.

Among the advantages of air travel, we can note the following:

- Speed and delivery time make this type of flight more frequent.
- You can cover multiple destinations and have the option of air transfers for easy access.
- This type of transport is more secure and reduces the possibility of theft.
- If the cost of transportation is significant, the transit time of goods will be reduced.

Disadvantages:

- The cost you have to pay for this type of transportation is higher than land and sea.
- Air transport has more cargo and storage capacity than land transport, but sea transport has more.
- In this case, there are restrictions on the products we can transport by air.
- Climate factors have a major impact on air transport as they can be at risk of flying in adverse weather conditions.

Significance.

- Air transportation is one of the most important because it is the safest means of transportation available today. It has great achievements in the field of telecommunications, which guarantees its security.

Reservation of seats and purchase of air tickets through airlines;

- booking seats and purchasing air tickets through reservation systems;
- agreement with the airline on the quota of seats in regular airlines;
- agency agreement and work as an agency for the sale of air tickets for their tourists;
- organization of charter flights for transportation of tourists.

In order to correctly choose the most convenient and profitable part of the transportation of tourists, as well as to conclude an agreement on the transportation of

tourists by air, you need to know all the features, advantages and disadvantages of one or another type of interaction with an airline.

Also, the travel agency should know the rules for booking air tickets, promotions, rates and discounts provided by airlines.

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